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Soil Water Repellency in Natural and Semi-Natural Habitats: A Nexus Between Abiotic Factors and Prokaryotic Communities

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ABSTRACT

Soil water repellency (SWR) significantly impacts water infiltration and soil health, influencing ecological processes across various habitats. Although the mechanisms behind SWR remain partially unclear, it is influenced by both soil and biological properties. While several studies have examined SWR in agricultural soils, fewer studies have focused on natural habitats. This study examines the relationships between soil properties (electrical conductivity (EC), pH, and total carbon (TC)), prokaryotic communities, and potential SWR (measured by the molarity of ethanol droplet test, 60°C pretreatment) in 1153 soil samples spanning 33 habitat types across Denmark. Using path model analysis, we show that both biotic and abiotic factors contribute significantly to SWR. A model including pH, EC, TC, and prokaryotic community composition (β -diversity) could explain ~50% of the variation in SWR, with β -diversity and TC being the most important properties. Furthermore, we reveal distinct variations in SWR across habitat types, which cover a wide range of SWR, from not water repellent to strongly water repellent. Prokaryotic α -diversity was negatively correlated to the degree of SWR, and we found a clear gradient in β -diversity from the highest to the lowest degree of SWR. The degree of SWR was divided into five classes, and we identified 69 genera indicating one or a combination of the SWR classes, which could potentially be used as indicators of the degree of SWR. This research underscores the importance of including the microbial communities in studies examining SWR. In perspective, the observed relations between SWR and soil prokaryotic diversity and community composition also imply that SWR could become a key biophysical indicator of soil health.

Abbreviations: Bogs, mires, and fens, raised bogs, mires, and fens; Coastal, coastal and halophytic habitats; Dunes, coastal sand dunes and inland dunes; EC, electrical conductivity; Grassland formations, natural and semi-natural grassland formations; IndVal, indicator value; NMDS, non-metric multidimensional scaling; pH, pH(CaCl₂); SWR, soil water repellency; TC, total carbon; Temperate heath and scrub, temperate heath and scrub and sclerophyllous scrub; VIF, variance inflation factor.

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Summary

- We examined soil properties, prokaryotic communities, and water repellency across natural habitats.
- Using 1153 samples we show that water repellency is common and varies within and among habitats.
- Soil water repellency was correlated with prokaryotic diversity and community composition.
- Biotic and abiotic properties influence water repellency, in particular carbon and prokaryotes.

1 | Introduction

Soil water repellency (SWR) occurs naturally and has been observed across climatic conditions (Doerr, Shakesby, and Walsh 2000) and different ecosystems, from natural and semi-natural habitats (Barrett and Slaymaker 1989; Dekker, Ritsema, and Oostindie 2000; Martínez-Zavala and Jordán-López 2009; Vogelmann et al. 2017) to agricultural systems (Blackwell 2000; de Jonge, Jacobsen, and Møldrup 1999; DeBano 2000; Dekker and Ritsema 1994). SWR varies temporally and spatially, as it is often higher in the warm and dry seasons when soil moisture is lower (Crockford, Topalidis, and Richardson 1991; Doerr, Shakesby, and Walsh 2000; Greiffenhagen et al. 2006), and it is not uniformly distributed in the landscape (Popović and Cerdà 2023). It impacts soil hydrology and can impede the infiltration of water in the soil (Coelho et al. 2005; DeBano 2000; Doerr and Thomas 2000; Smettem et al. 2021; Urbanek, Walsh, and Shakesby 2015; Zheng et al. 2017), leading to increased runoff and increased erosion (Lowe, McGrath, and Leopold 2021; Sheridan, Lane, and Noske 2007). However, in natural habitats SWR may enhance water infiltration if large macropores are present, as these pores can act as preferential flow paths, allowing for deeper infiltration (Lebron et al. 2007; Robinson et al. 2010). In managed systems, SWR can have negative effects on plant growth and overall productivity (Blackwell 2000; Li et al. 2019; Popović and Cerdà 2023), but recent studies suggest that SWR can be an adaptive trait in natural systems (Ruthrof et al. 2019; Seaton et al. 2019). Some plant species utilise SWR to store water deeper in the soil through preferential flow paths, thereby reducing the water lost to evaporation (Robinson et al. 2010). Additionally, both plants and fungi may gain competitive advantages from altering soil water dynamics. By increasing the degree of SWR, fungi can outcompete other organisms not able to thrive and reproduce in dry conditions (Unestam 1991). Deep-rooted plants will gain an advantage by storing water at deeper layers, as it will be unavailable to plants with shallower root systems (Robinson et al. 2010). Thus, SWR's role in ecosystem functioning is multifaceted, and understanding its significance is critical, especially in the context of climate change, where extreme climatic events such as droughts, heat waves, and altered precipitation patterns are expected to affect SWR (Goebel et al. 2011; Popović and Cerdà 2023).

Despite its ecological importance, the mechanisms behind SWR are still unclear, as SWR is a dynamic property and is affected by numerous properties of the hydrosphere, lithosphere, biosphere, and atmosphere (Smettem et al. 2021). Several studies have shown that soil properties such as texture, pH, and

organic carbon content can influence SWR (Chau et al. 2014; de Jonge, Jacobsen, and Møldrup 1999; Hermansen et al. 2019; Karunarathna et al. 2010; Weber et al. 2021). The degree of SWR is correlated with the carbon content of the soil, but also the chemical composition or quality of the carbon (de Jonge, Møldrup, and Jacobsen 2007; Fu et al. 2021). While the relationship between SWR and carbon is well-established, the role of pH has received less attention. Some studies have shown that pH plays a role in the development and persistence of SWR, which generally increases with acidification (Martínez-Zavala and Jordán-López 2009; Mataix-Solera et al. 2007; Mataix-Solera and Doerr 2004). Acidic conditions promote the ionisation of hydrophobic organic molecules, such as fatty acids, facilitating their adsorption to soil surfaces and increasing water repellency (Graber, Tagger, and Wallach 2009; Peng, Barnes, and Gentle 2001). The relationship between SWR and pH is likely context-dependent, influenced by interactions with other soil properties, including texture, aluminium availability, and the composition of organic matter (de Jonge, Jacobsen, and Møldrup 1999; Graber, Tagger, and Wallach 2009).

There is a strong link between vegetation and SWR (Popović and Cerdà 2023; Šurda et al. 2020; Zema et al. 2021) as water repellent compounds produced by plants influence the degree of SWR (Chai et al. 2024; de Blas, Almendros, and Sanz 2013; Doerr, Shakesby, and Walsh 2000; Franco et al. 2000). Specific plant species and traits have been associated with a higher degree of SWR (Popović and Cerdà 2023), and some studies suggest that SWR can play a role in competition (Popović and Cerdà 2023; Ruwanza and Dondofema 2020) and stress tolerance (Gao et al. 2018; Seaton et al. 2019). The degree of SWR has also been linked to microbial communities (Chai et al. 2022; Doerr, Shakesby, and Walsh 2000; Majid et al. 2023; Seaton et al. 2019) in particular to the fungi (Hallett, Ritz, and Wheatley 2001; Unestam 1991; Unestam and Sun 1995). Microbial communities contribute significantly to the soil's organic carbon content, with microbial necromass potentially making up more than half of the organic carbon content in some soils (Liang et al. 2019). While the living part of microbial communities typically accounts for a smaller proportion (Patoine et al. 2022), they further affect the carbon pool by decomposition and transformation of plant residue released into the soil (Wu et al. 2024). However, the relationship between microorganisms and SWR is not straightforward, as specific microbes can increase SWR (Chai et al. 2022; Seaton et al. 2019), while others are able to reduce SWR by degrading the water repellent compounds (Liu et al. 2013; Roper 2005; Simpson et al. 2019). Furthermore, ectomycorrhizal fungi exhibit both hydrophobic and hydrophilic properties and can either increase SWR through the formation of water-repellent mats or decrease SWR by absorbing and translocating water in wet soil conditions (Unestam 1991; Unestam and Sun 1995). SWR is thus affected by the composition and activity of microbial communities (Simpson et al. 2019), but SWR can also affect microbial communities (Lozano et al. 2014). While the role of fungi is well established in relation to SWR, less is known about the roles of the prokaryotes. In a recent study by Karagulyan et al. (2022), water-stress-induced changes in bacterial cell structure lead to an increase in water repellency of the cell surface, which is assumed to contribute further to soil SWR. Thus, prokaryotic communities might also influence the degree of SWR.

This study aims to explore the degree of potential SWR (Dekker and Ritsema 1994; Kajiura, Tokida, and Seki 2012) and the abiotic and biotic factors influencing it, with a particular focus on prokaryotic communities. Using 1153 soil samples from the Microflora Danica project (Singleton et al. 2024), we assess how SWR varies among different natural and semi-natural habitats and its relationship with key soil properties (pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total carbon content (TC)) and prokaryotic communities. The samples represent 30 natural and semi-natural habitat types, following the Habitats Directive Annex I typology and three additional broader forest types. We hypothesize that SWR varies within and among different habitat types and is influenced by differences in biological and environmental conditions. Specifically, we hypothesize that (i) SWR varies within and among natural and semi-natural habitats, driven by differences in biological communities and environmental conditions, and (ii) there is an interplay between prokaryotic communities and SWR which influences the degree of SWR, in combination with soil properties. We aim to answer the following research questions:

- i. How does soil water repellency vary within and among natural and semi-natural habitats across Denmark, and is it, at a national scale, related to the total carbon content?
- ii. Is there an association between soil water repellency and prokaryotic α - and β -diversity?

- iii. Which biotic (prokaryotic α - and β -diversity) and abiotic (TC, pH, EC) properties influence the degree of SWR?
- iv. Can prokaryotic genera be used as indicators of the degree of SWR?

By addressing these questions, we aim to shed light on the distribution and degree of SWR among and within natural and semi-natural habitats and the influence of prokaryotic communities on SWR, offering insights into a less examined part of the microbial communities.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Locations and Sampling

In total, 1153 samples were collected across Denmark, covering natural and semi-natural habitats (Figure 1). Denmark is a northern European country, covering approximately 43,000 km². The country has a temperate climate, with average winter and summer temperatures of 0°C and 16°C, respectively, annual precipitation of approximately 800 mm. During late autumn, winter, and early spring, precipitation often surpasses evapotranspiration. Denmark was shaped by several glaciations during the quaternary period, leading to the formation of complex glacial landscapes. Soil types range from coarse sand in the west to loamy soils in the east (Gomes et al. 2023).

FIGURE 1 | Map of sampling locations coloured by habitat type. One sample was collected from each of the 1153 locations (NB: Not all 1153 points are visible on the map due to some points overlapping others). Habitat types were classified according to the Habitats Directive Annex I typology and the map shows the habitat types at the highest level.

Furthermore, all locations were classified into habitat types. The classification of habitats was organised into two hierarchical levels (Table S1). At the higher level, the habitats were categorised into broad habitat groups (e.g., forests, dunes, coastal habitats) representing general habitat types that are commonly recognised in ecological studies. At the finer level, each of the broad habitat groups was further subdivided into specific habitat types, corresponding to the typology from the Habitats Directive Annex I (Table S1), except for 202 locations which were categorised into broader categories of forests: deciduous, coniferous, and non-native.

In each location, five subsamples were collected at 0–20 cm depth and pooled into one sample, stored in a sterile plastic container. Prior to sample collection, vegetation and litter were removed. In the field, samples were stored in a cool box and then stored at -20°C after arrival at the laboratory. A subsample from each pooled sample was used for DNA extraction and metagenomic sequencing, while the rest of the sample was stored at 2°C until analysis of potential SWR, TC content, pH, and EC.

2.2 | Analysis of Soil Physico-Chemical Properties

Prior to the measurement of soil physico-chemical properties, soil samples were air-dried and sieved to 2 mm. The content of TC was measured by dry combustion, using a Vario MAX cube (Elementar Analysensysteme AG). Further, pH was measured in a soil:CaCl₂ suspension of 1:4 (v/v), and EC was determined in a soil: water suspension of 1:10 (v/v). For SWR measurements, a subsample of each sample was oven-dried at 60°C and then left to equilibrate for 48 h at 20°C . The molarity of an ethanol droplet test (Roy and McGill 2002) was used to measure the degree of SWR following the procedure described in de Jonge, Møldrup, and Jacobsen (2007). The method followed the procedures described by Hermansen et al. (2019) and Weber et al. (2021). Droplets of $60\ \mu\text{L}$, containing ethanol solutions at concentrations ranging from 0 to $0.80\ \text{cm}^3\ \text{cm}^{-3}$, were applied to the soil surface. The degree of SWR, expressed as surface tension (mN m^{-1}), was determined based on the highest ethanol concentration that did not infiltrate the soil within 5 s (Roy and McGill 2002). Water repellent soils are characterised by a lower surface tension compared to non-repellent soils. The addition of ethanol progressively reduces the surface tension of the applied droplets. Non-repellent soils are associated with a surface tension of $71.276\ \text{mN m}^{-1}$, while surface tensions below this threshold indicate increasing levels of SWR, with more severe repellency corresponding to lower liquid surface tensions. As samples were dried prior to measurement, the degree of SWR represents the potential SWR (Dekker and Ritsema 1994; Kajiura, Tokida, and Seki 2012), which can be used to compare the degree of SWR among soils. A summary of TC, EC, pH, and SWR can be found in Table S2.

Samples were assigned to one of five categories based on the degree of SWR (Table 1). The classification was based on the definition of extreme SWR by Doerr, Shakesby, and Walsh (2000), where soils with a degree of SWR $< 40.9\ \text{mN m}^{-1}$, were classified as “extremely hydrophobic”. The other subdivisions were defined using a fixed interval, calculated by dividing the difference

TABLE 1 | Overview of soil water repellency (SWR) classes and number of samples within each class.

Category	SWR (mN m^{-1})	Number of samples	Proportion
No SWR	71.27	266	23%
Mild	61.1–71.27	87	8%
Moderate	51.0–61.1	210	18%
High	40.9–51.0	490	42%
Extreme	< 40.9	100	9%

between the no SWR and extreme SWR categories with the number of other categories.

2.3 | DNA Extraction and Sequencing

The following is a brief description of the methods used for extracting and sequencing DNA from the soil samples and the reader is referred to Singleton et al. (2024) for a thorough description of the library preparation, sequencing and processing. Briefly, DNA was extracted using the DNeasy 96 PowerSoil Pro QIAcube HT Kit, and metagenome libraries were sequenced on the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina Inc.). Raw 150 bp paired-end reads were processed by fastp (Chen et al. 2018) using GNU parallel (Tange 2022) to trim barcodes, quality filter and deduplicate. The short-read 16S rRNA gene sequences were recovered as described by Singleton et al. (2024), with 16S rRNA gene fragments extracted using seqkit and HMMER (Eddy 2011) and Hidden Markov Models generated from RFAM archaeal and bacterial seed alignments (Kalvari et al. 2021). Reads were selected based on the best nhmmer bit-score. Reads were classified using SINTAX (Edgar 2016), and the Microflora Global reference database clustered at 98.7% sequence identity (Singleton et al. 2024).

2.4 | Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed in R (R Core Team 2022) version 4.3.0, and a significance level of 0.05 was used unless otherwise stated.

The phylo-table was pre-processed prior to any analysis. Firstly, data was aggregated to genus level, and the read counts were plotted to identify the minimum library size. Samples were then rarefied to 1486 reads per sample, based on the sample with the lowest read count. Lastly, the read counts were transformed to relative abundance and non-classified phylotypes were discarded. Shannon's diversity index (Shannon 1948) was calculated as a measure of prokaryotic α -diversity, that is, the diversity within a sample (Andermann et al. 2022; Whittaker 1960) by using the formula:

$$1 - \sum pi \cdot \log(pi) \quad (1)$$

where pi is the proportional abundance of genus i . Shannon's diversity index considers not only the richness, but also the evenness of the genera. Shannon's diversity index was calculated

using the R-package Vegan (Oksanen et al. 2013). Violin-plots overlaid with boxplots were used to visualise the difference in SWR among habitat types and in Shannon's diversity index among SWR-classes. Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) analysis (Legendre and Legendre 2012) was used to examine prokaryotic β -diversity (i.e., the dissimilarity in community composition among samples (Andermann et al. 2022)) and the association with SWR-classes. Before ordination, the community data was transformed and standardised by square root transformation and Wisconsin double standardisation (Oksanen et al. 2013). A dissimilarity matrix was calculated using the Bray–Curtis dissimilarity measure (Bray and Curtis 1957) and used as input for the ordination. No phylotypes were removed before ordination. The ordination was performed using the R-package Vegan (Oksanen et al. 2013).

Path analysis was used to examine the relationship between SWR and biological (α - and β -diversity) and soil physico-chemical (TC, EC and pH) properties. Path analysis is a statistical method within structural equation modelling that examines the linear relationships between observed variables and is typically illustrated by a path diagram, where the variables are shown as boxes connected by arrows, representing the relationships (Valenzuela and Bachmann 2017). Multicollinearity among the variables was addressed by making a linear regression and calculating Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), and only variables with a VIF below 4 were included in the final path analysis. The path analysis was generated using the R-package Lavaan (Rosseel 2012), and separate analyses were conducted for α - and β -diversity, using the following linear equations:

$$\text{SWR} \sim \alpha + \text{TC} + \text{pH} + \text{EC} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{SWR} \sim \beta + \text{TC} + \text{pH} + \text{EC} \quad (3)$$

Since SWR was not normally distributed bootstrapping (Berrar and Dubitzky 2013) ($n=1000$) was employed to provide robust estimates and confidence intervals. As the number of estimated parameters in the models matches the number of unique data points the models are just-identified or saturated. As a result, there are no degrees of freedom left for model testing and fit indices such as chi-square or RMSEA are not applicable for evaluating model fit (Valenzuela and Bachmann 2017).

Indicator organisms are those that exhibit a strong association with specific environmental conditions or ecological groups (Dufrêne and Legendre 1997). Prokaryotic genera indicating one or a combination of the SWR classes were identified by calculating their indicator value (IndVal), which combines both the frequency and specificity of their occurrence within the classes (Cáceres and Legendre 2009; Dufrêne and Legendre 1997). A high IndVal signifies that the genus is strongly associated to a particular SWR class (or a combination of these). The indicator genera were identified using the Indicspecies package for R (Cáceres and Legendre 2009) with 9999 permutations. To account for the unequal number of samples within the SWR classes, `func="IndVal.g"` from the `multipatt`-function was used. Only genera with an indicator statistic (IndVal) higher than 0.6 were included, as organisms with an IndVal below 0.5 are not specific to a given class (Boutin et al. 2021; Chu et al. 2017; Dufrêne and Legendre 1997). Due to the multiple testing, p -values were

corrected as recommended by Legendre (2013), using the Benjamin–Hochberg method (Benjamini and Hochberg 1995).

3 | Results

3.1 | Soil Water Repellency in Natural and Semi-Natural Habitats

Some degree of SWR was observed for 77% of the samples, with the majority of these being moderately to highly water repellent (Table 1). The degree of SWR varied among and within habitat types (Figure 2) and a large variation was seen at the highest level of habitat classification (Figure 2A,B,D–F) except for heathland and scrub where all or most samples exhibited moderate to extreme SWR (Figure 2C). A moderate or high degree of SWR was observed for all habitat types, apart from habitat type 2110 (Embryonic shifting dunes) where samples only showed mild SWR (Figure 2E).

The degree of SWR was related to TC; samples with a higher TC content generally had higher degree of SWR (Figure 3A,B). However, large variations in SWR were observed for samples with the lowest TC contents, and the relationship between SWR and TC was most evident for the samples with the highest degree of SWR. The variation in SWR among samples with a relatively low carbon content was to some degree related to habitat type (Figure 3B), for example habitat types 2130 (Fixed coastal dunes with herbaceous vegetation) (Figure 3C) and 6120 (Xeric sand calcareous grasslands) (Figure 3D). In other habitat types, samples showed a high degree of SWR at all TC contents, for example, habitat types 2140 (Decalcified fixed dunes with *Empetrum nigrum*) (Figure 3C), 4030 (European dry heaths) (Figure 3E) and, with the exception of a few samples, 4010 (Northern Atlantic wet heaths with *Erica tetralix*) (Figure 3E). For other habitats, the relationship between SWR and TC content was less clear-cut, for example 6430 (Hydrophilous tall herb fringe communities of plains and of the montane to alpine levels) (Figure 3D).

3.2 | Relationship Between SWR and Prokaryotes

The prokaryotic α -diversity, measured as Shannon's diversity index, differed between SWR-classes. In general, α -diversity was highest in soils with no or mild repellency and lowest in the soils with extreme SWR (Figure 4).

The relationship between prokaryotes and SWR was also evident for β -diversity (Figure 5), which was examined using NMDS ordinations based on Bray–Curtis dissimilarity. Although the samples did not form distinct groups corresponding to the SWR-classes, there is a clear gradient from the extreme/high repellency to mild/no repellency along the first dimension.

3.3 | Biotic and Abiotic Properties Influencing SWR

To examine the properties influencing SWR, a path model was used to examine how well SWR could be explained by

FIGURE 2 | Visualisation (violin-plots overlaid by boxplots) of the range of soil water repellency, mN m^{-1} (SWR) within the habitat types. Habitat types are classified according to the Habitats Directive Annex I typology, and the figure is divided into subplots based on the highest level of the typology. The habitat codes given on the x-axes correspond to the habitat codes from the Directive (Table S1), except for some forest samples, which were only possible to classify into coniferous, deciduous, and non-native trees (habitat codes 99**). Data originates 1153 soil samples collected in natural and semi-natural habitats across Denmark. The sample size for each habitat type is given above the plots. Shaded areas behind the violin-plots are coloured according to SWR class (light green = mild, yellow = moderate, orange = high, red = extreme). The y-axes have been reversed, so each plot starts at non-repellent values of SWR, going to a higher degree of SWR.

soil properties and prokaryotic α - and β -diversity, respectively. Prokaryotic α -diversity, TC, pH and EC could explain 47.9% of the variation in SWR (Figure 6A), with TC and pH being the strongest predictors. The use of β -diversity instead of α -diversity, led to a slightly better performance of the model, which could explain 49.9% of the variation in SWR (Figure 6B), with β -diversity and TC being the strongest predictors.

3.4 | Prokaryotic Genera as Indicators of SWR Classes

Using a threshold indicator value (Indval) of 0.6, as previously suggested (Boutin et al. 2021; Chu et al. 2017), we identified 69

prokaryotic genera indicating a specific SWR class or a combination of classes (Table 2). Indicator genera belonged to 13 phyla, with the majority indicating a combination of the classes with the smallest degree of SWR (Actinobacteriota, Bacteroidota, Chloroflexi, Gemmatimonadota, Methylomirabilota, Myxococcota, Nitrospirota, Planctomycetota, and RCP2-54). One genus belonging to the phylum WPS-2 indicated the strongest degree of SWR, while genera belonging to Acidobacteriota, Proteobacteria, and Verrucomicrobiota were indicating either the smallest or largest degree of SWR. Among the indicators of the highest degree of SWR (high + extreme), only one genus, *Acidicaldus*, has an accepted name, while the other genera were novel with placeholder names. For all SWR classes, approximately half of the identified indicator genera belong to novel genera.

FIGURE 3 | Relationship between soil water repellency, mN m^{-1} (SWR) and binned total carbon, kg kg^{-1} (TC) (A). TC content was binned into intervals of 0.02, for TC values between 0 and 0.16 kg kg^{-1} , and intervals of 0.05 for TC values above 0.16 kg kg^{-1} . The boundary values are included in the bin to their left, that is, 0.02 is included in the 0–0.02 bin etc. Relationship between SWR, TC, and habitat type across all samples (B) and within selected habitat types (C–E). Data originates 1153 soil samples collected in natural and semi-natural habitats across Denmark, but only a subset is used for C, D, and E. Habitat types are classified following the Habitats Directive Annex I typology (Table S1). On B, samples are coloured according to the highest level of the typology from the Habitats Directive. The y-axes have been reversed, so each plot starts at non-repellent values of SWR, going to a higher degree of SWR. On (A), the sample size for each bin is given above the boxplots.

FIGURE 4 | Visualisation (violin-plots overlaid by boxplots) of the range of α -diversity, measured as Shannon's diversity index, within the soil water repellency (SWR) classes (No SWR: 71.27 mN m⁻¹, mild: 61.1–71.27 mN m⁻¹, moderate: 51.0–61.1 mN m⁻¹, high: 40.9–51.0 mN m⁻¹, extreme: <40.9 mN m⁻¹). The sample size for each class is given above the violin-plots. Data originates 1153 soil samples collected in natural and semi-natural habitats across Denmark. Plots are coloured according to the SWR classes.

4 | Discussion

4.1 | Soil Water Repellency Is Widespread but Varies Within Natural and Semi-Natural Habitats

We observed some degree of SWR in most samples, which was also observed in natural habitats by Seaton et al. (2019), and different forest types by Chai et al. (2022). It has been established that SWR is widespread (Doerr and Ritsema 2006; Jordán et al. 2013) and no longer considered the exception but rather the norm for soils across different soil and vegetation types (Danielsen et al. 2023; DeBano 2000; Doerr and Ritsema 2006; Doerr, Shakesby, and Walsh 2000), which is also reflected in our findings. The degree of SWR varied among and within habitat types, in agreement with a previous study that examined SWR across Wales (Seaton et al. 2019). The variations observed in the present study, within the highest level of habitat classification and among habitat types in general, most likely reflect differences in texture, TC content, hydrology, and the diversity and composition of the biological communities, as these properties vary among the habitat types (European Commission 2013). As the ability to induce SWR varies between plant species (Doerr, Shakesby, and Walsh 2000; Popović and Cerdà 2023), the different plant communities found in the habitat types are assumed to contribute to the variations in SWR. As an example, some habitat types are dominated by grasses and sedges, which are known to produce water repellent substances (Majid et al. 2023). Less is known about the variations in prokaryotic community composition among habitat types. However, given the association between above- and below-ground communities (van der Putten et al. 2009), the variation in soil properties and plant communities among the habitat types, the prokaryotic communities are assumed to differ among habitat types, also suggested by previous work (Danielsen et al. 2023). Prokaryotic communities

FIGURE 5 | Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) showing the variation in prokaryotic community composition and the association with soil water repellency (SWR) classes (No SWR: 71.27 mN m⁻¹, mild: 61.1–71.27 mN m⁻¹, moderate: 51.0–61.1 mN m⁻¹, high: 40.9–51.0 mN m⁻¹, extreme: <40.9 mN m⁻¹). The NMDS ordination was generated based on the Bray–Curtis dissimilarity measure (Bray and Curtis 1957) of 25,717 genera in the 1153 samples from natural and semi-natural habitats in Denmark. Prior to the analysis, data were rarefied to 1486 reads and transformed by calculating relative abundance. Samples are coloured according to SWR class.

participate in the decomposition of organic material, which can lead to an increase or decrease in SWR, depending on the community composition (Chai et al. 2022; Liu et al. 2013; McKenna et al. 2002; Roper 2005; Simpson et al. 2019). Furthermore, the production of water repellent products (Schaumann et al. 2007) and changes in cell structure leading to a higher degree of water repellency (Karagulyan et al. 2022) can further contribute to SWR, depending on the community composition. Thus, the variations in SWR observed within and among habitat types are most likely a combined effect of prokaryotic and plant communities, as well as soil properties.

In alkaline soils, inorganic carbon sources such as calcium carbonate can provide calcium ions that enhance SWR by forming hydrophobic compounds with organic molecules (Graber, Tagger, and Wallach 2009). Using TC, we account for the contributions of organic and inorganic carbon to SWR, including pH-dependent interactions which is necessary given the large range in pH in the present study (Table S2). We found that the degree of SWR was related to TC content, consistent with the findings in previous studies (Hermansen et al. 2019; Mao et al. 2019; Seaton et al. 2019; Weber et al. 2021). However, large variations in SWR were observed for samples with the lowest TC contents, which seems to be related to habitat types characterised by sandy soils. Because of the small surface area of sandy soils, only a small amount of water repellent substances are required to coat the particles, which can explain why SWR is observed for samples with a relatively low TC content (Crockford, Topalidis, and Richardson 1991; de Jonge, Jacobsen, and Møldrup 1999; DeBano 1981). An additional explanation is the difference in

FIGURE 6 | Path analysis model of soil properties and prokaryotic α -diversity, (A) and β -diversity, (B) as predictors of soil water repellency, mNm^{-1} (SWR). The properties included in the analysis can explain 47.9 (A) and 49.4% (B) of the variation in soil water repellency (SWR). Solid lines indicate regressions between the predictors and SWR. Dashed lines indicate covariance between predictors. The colour of the lines indicates if the correlations are positive (green) or negative (red). The strength of the regression is indicated by the thickness of the lines. For each predictor, regression parameters are given, and significance is indicated by * (* = 0.05, ** = 0.01, *** = 0.001). Data originates 1153 soil samples collected in natural and semi-natural habitats across Denmark. EC = electrical conductivity (dS m^{-1}), pH = $\text{pH}(\text{CaCl}_2)$, TC = total carbon (kg kg^{-1}), α = α -diversity (Shannon's diversity index), β = β -diversity (first dimension from NMDS analysis).

the community composition of plants and prokaryotes. As previously mentioned, the degree of water repellent material varies among plant species (Doerr, Shakesby, and Walsh 2000; Popović and Cerdà 2023) and some prokaryotes can increase SWR (Chai et al. 2022; Seaton et al. 2019) while others decrease it (Liu et al. 2013; Roper 2005; Simpson et al. 2019), leading to differences in the compounds released to the soil via these communities. Furthermore, studies have shown that not only the amount of organic matter but also the composition, or quality, influences the degree of SWR (de Jonge, Møldrup, and Jacobsen 2007; Fu et al. 2021).

4.2 | Associations Between SWR and Prokaryotic α - and β -Diversity

We found a negative relationship between the degree of SWR and prokaryotic α -diversity, a trend which was also observed in the study by Chai et al. (2022), where the lowest bacterial α -diversity was found in samples collected beneath *Pinus*, the vegetation type with the highest degree of SWR. The low diversity in the samples with the highest degree of SWR could imply that these soils comprise a stressful environment. Conversely, the lower α -diversity could also be contributing to the increased SWR, as the prokaryotes responsible for breaking down water repellent compounds, thereby decreasing SWR, might be missing from these communities (Chai et al. 2022). However, the negative relationship observed between prokaryotic α -diversity and SWR could also be a co-correlation with pH. For β -diversity, we found a clear gradient from the extreme/high repellency to mild/no repellency along the first dimension of the NMDS-ordination, suggesting an association between the degree of SWR and prokaryotic community composition. A high degree of SWR can be a source of stress to the prokaryotic community, and several studies have concluded that stress influences microbial community composition,

for example water stress (Fierer, Schimel, and Holden 2003; Zhang, Yao, and Hu 2007). Fewer studies have examined the influence of SWR on community composition. However, SWR was found to affect bacterial β -diversity by O'Brien et al. (2019) and bacterial and fungal β -diversity Chai et al. (2022). Further research is needed to improve our understanding of the effect of SWR on microbial community composition, and vice versa.

4.3 | SWR Is Influenced by Carbon and β -Diversity in Natural and Semi-Natural Habitats

A strong association was found between SWR and prokaryotic communities and TC content, respectively. Notably, prokaryotic β -diversity was a stronger predictor of SWR compared with TC (Figure 6). While it is well established that SWR is related to soil carbon content, the influence of prokaryotic communities is less examined. The findings of the present paper agree with the study by Seaton et al. (2019), where bacterial composition had a direct effect on SWR, comparable to that of carbon.

In the present paper, we focused on the prokaryotic communities but including the fungi, in addition to prokaryotes, would most likely have improved the path analysis. Given the influence of fungal communities on SWR (Unestam 1991; Unestam and Sun 1995) and the results presented here, future studies should include fungi and prokaryotes. Seaton et al. (2019) proposed that the ability of an ecosystem to induce SWR is a stress response, and SWR in natural ecosystems could increase resilience. Thus, the SWR found in the natural and semi-natural habitats in the present paper could indicate health and ability to adapt to stressful conditions and could be a potential indicator of soil health. Rillig et al. (2019) found that SWR was increased by multiple global change stressors, further implying that SWR could be a useful parameter for monitoring soil health, particularly under

TABLE 2 | Prokaryotic genera indicating one or a combination of soil water repellency (SWR) classes.

Indicator genera	Phylum	IndVal	No SWR	Mild	Moderate	High	Extreme
MFD_g_8204	Acidobacteriota	0.869	■	■	■		
<i>Nocardioides</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.866	■	■	■		
Pir4_lineage	Planctomycetota	0.83	■	■	■		
<i>Gemmatimonas</i>	Gemmatimonadota	0.821	■	■	■		
Subgroup_10	Acidobacteriota	0.803	■	■	■		
<i>Flavobacterium</i>	Bacteroidota	0.783	■	■	■		
MFD_g_5535	Chloroflexi	0.782	■	■	■		
MFD_g_812	Actinobacteriota	0.776	■	■	■		
MFD_g_6	Proteobacteria	0.771	■	■	■		
<i>Gaiella</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.77	■	■	■		
Ellin6067	Proteobacteria	0.757	■	■	■		
<i>Pedomicrobium</i>	Proteobacteria	0.752	■	■	■		
MFD_g_678	Actinobacteriota	0.751	■	■	■		
<i>Hyphomicrobium</i>	Proteobacteria	0.746	■	■	■		
<i>Pirellula</i>	Planctomycetota	0.746	■	■	■		
Ca_Alysiosphaera	Proteobacteria	0.738	■	■	■		
CL500-29_marine_group	Actinobacteriota	0.736	■	■	■		
<i>Acidicaldus</i>	Proteobacteria	0.735				■	■
MFD_g_782	Chloroflexi	0.734	■	■	■		
<i>Iamia</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.732	■	■	■		
<i>Solirubrobacter</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.729	■	■	■		
MFD_g_13520	Actinobacteriota	0.729	■	■	■		
<i>Microbacterium</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.727	■	■	■		
<i>Nitrospira</i>	Nitrospirota	0.726	■	■	■		
<i>Sphingomonas</i>	Proteobacteria	0.722	■	■	■		
<i>Ferruginibacter</i>	Bacteroidota	0.72	■	■	■		
MFD_g_264	Actinobacteriota	0.711	■	■	■		
MFD_g_650	Actinobacteriota	0.704	■	■	■		
<i>Pseudomonas</i>	Proteobacteria	0.696	■	■	■		
<i>Bauldia</i>	Proteobacteria	0.692	■	■	■		
MFD_g_875	Myxococcota	0.689	■	■	■		
MFD_g_3931	WPS-2	0.688				■	■
MFD_g_6265	Acidobacteriota	0.688	■	■	■		
MFD_g_1081	Actinobacteriota	0.682	■	■	■		
MFD_g_35850	Verrucomicrobiota	0.678			■	■	■
MFD_g_11470	Acidobacteriota	0.678	■	■	■		
<i>Allorhizobium-Neorhizobium-Pararhizobium-Rhizobium</i>	Proteobacteria	0.678	■	■	■		

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Indicator genera	Phylum	IndVal	No SWR	Mild	Moderate	High	Extreme
<i>Ilumatobacter</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.677	■	■	■		
MFD_g_2480	Proteobacteria	0.674	■	■	■		
MFD_g_2431	Acidobacteriota	0.666	■	■	■		
<i>Marmoricola</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.666	■	■	■		
RB41	Acidobacteriota	0.661	■	■	■		
MFD_g_191	Actinobacteriota	0.659	■	■	■		
<i>Luteolibacter</i>	Verrucomicrobiota	0.656	■	■	■		
MND1	Proteobacteria	0.649	■	■	■		
MFD_g_9823	Chloroflexi	0.649	■	■	■		
<i>Rhodoplanes</i>	Proteobacteria	0.648	■	■	■		
MFD_g_2884	RCP2-54	0.647	■	■	■		
MFD_g_579	Acidobacteriota	0.636					■
<i>Rhodococcus</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.632	■	■	■		
MFD_g_1794	Actinobacteriota	0.631	■	■	■		
MFD_g_619	Actinobacteriota	0.63	■	■	■		
MFD_g_13437	Verrucomicrobiota	0.628				■	■
MFD_g_4485	Acidobacteriota	0.626	■	■	■		
<i>Microlunatus</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.625	■	■	■		
MFD_g_60423	Acidobacteriota	0.623				■	■
MFD_g_378425	Acidobacteriota	0.622					■
<i>Rhizobacter</i>	Proteobacteria	0.62	■	■	■		
MFD_g_13790	Acidobacteriota	0.618	■	■	■		
MFD_g_11217	Acidobacteriota	0.618	■	■	■		
SM1A02	Planctomycetota	0.616	■	■	■		
<i>Phaselicystis</i>	Myxococcota	0.615	■	■	■		
MFD_g_4431	Methylomirabilota	0.615	■	■	■		
MFD_g_841	Actinobacteriota	0.607	■	■	■		
MFD_g_4557	Proteobacteria	0.606	■	■	■		
MFD_g_1742	Actinobacteriota	0.605	■	■	■		
<i>Luedemannella</i>	Actinobacteriota	0.603	■	■	■		
MFD_g_3171	Acidobacteriota	0.602	■	■	■		
mle1-7	Proteobacteria	0.6	■	■	■		

Note: The first two columns list the genera and phylum, while the third column contains the indicator values (IndVal), that is, the strength of the association between the indicator organism and the SWR class(es). The SWR class(es) associated with a genus is indicated with a black square for the five right-most columns. Columns are coloured according to SWR class.

the pressures of climate change and land-use change. However, additional work is needed to further elucidate the mechanisms behind SWR and what can be considered a 'healthy' level of SWR in the habitats.

Using α -diversity instead of β -diversity led to a slightly lower performance of the model and pH became a much stronger

predictor. This is most likely reflecting the strong relationship between pH and β -diversity (Chu et al. 2020; Delgado-Baquerizo et al. 2018; George et al. 2019). The effect of soil pH on SWR remains poorly understood, but Graber, Tagger, and Wallach (2009) showed that SWR was affected by pH and the presence of cations. As previously mentioned, the presence of inorganic carbon can enhance SWR by forming hydrophobic compounds with organic

molecules in alkaline soils (Graber, Tagger, and Wallach 2009). In acidic soils, the influence of aluminium on SWR is indirectly linked to the carbon pool, as aluminium ions can interact with organic matter to enhance hydrophobicity. SWR is generally more persistent in acidic soils than in alkaline soils, with repellency increasing as pH decreases (Mataix-Solera et al. 2007; Mataix-Solera and Doerr 2004). This is likely linked to the chemical structure of fatty acids and other organic compounds, which is pH-dependent, providing a potential causal link between soil pH and SWR (Graber, Tagger, and Wallach 2009). While a negative correlation has been found between pH and SWR (de Jonge, Jacobsen, and Møldrup 1999) other studies found no significant relationships between SWR and pH (Deurer et al. 2011; Hermansen et al. 2019). In the present paper, pH was identified as a significant predictor of SWR, but less important than TC and prokaryotic β -diversity.

4.4 | Prokaryotic Genera Can Indicate the Degree of SWR

Several genera indicating one or a combination of SWR classes were identified, with the majority indicating a low degree of SWR (no SWR + mild + moderate). Approximately half of the indicators were novel genera and only possible to include due to the newly established Microflora Global reference database (Singleton et al. 2024). Most of the indicator genera suggested a combination of SWR classes, only two genera indicating a single SWR class were identified, both indicating extreme SWR. This suggests that the prokaryotes, in general, can tolerate a range of water repellency, and the SWR classes used in the present paper are narrower than this range, except for the extreme class. Actinobacteriota has previously been associated with a higher degree of SWR (Braun et al. 2010; Chai et al. 2022), but in the present paper they were indicators of the mildest degree of SWR. *Acidicaldus* was the only genus with an accepted name indicating severe SWR (high + extreme). This genus was described by Johnson et al. (2006), who found it in samples from geothermal sites, which suggests that this genus is able to adapt to extreme environments. Further studies are needed to elucidate the relationship between specific prokaryotes and the degree of SWR, using more in-depth examinations of the functions of the prokaryotes and how they increase or decrease SWR. The indicators identified in the present paper could be a starting point for these studies.

5 | Conclusion

In the present study, we showed a strong relationship between SWR, TC, pH and biological communities.

We found large variations in the degree of SWR among and within habitat types. Across habitat types, most of the samples showed some degree of SWR. The degree of SWR was related to TC content, however, this relationship was most evident for samples with the highest degree of SWR and varied among habitat types. The variation in SWR among samples with the lowest TC content was related to habitat type, most likely reflecting differences in texture, hydrology, and input from the biological communities, which differ among habitat types.

We identified associations between SWR-classes and prokaryotic α - and β -diversity. In general, α -diversity was negatively correlated to the degree of SWR, that is, a high degree of SWR is associated with lower α -diversity. For β -diversity, a clear gradient was observed from the least to the most severe SWR, most likely reflecting that the highest degree of SWR represents a stressful environment for the prokaryotes, driving changes in community composition.

We identified the abiotic and biotic properties influencing the degree of SWR in natural and semi-natural areas. Almost half of the variations in SWR could be explained by a model including prokaryotic β -diversity, TC content, pH, and EC, with β -diversity and TC being the strongest predictors. Furthermore, we identified 69 prokaryotic genera indicating one or a combination of SWR classes, which could be a starting point for future studies examining the contribution of these genera to the increase or decrease in SWR.

Future studies should address the limitations in the present study. First, we only measured potential soil water repellency, and there could be important SWR dynamics at other water potentials. Second, we did not have information on soil texture, which is known to be a significant factor influencing SWR, and it was not possible to include the proportion of organic and inorganic carbon in the samples. Third, this study focused on the relative composition of the prokaryotes, while the amount of prokaryotic biomass was not considered. Future research addressing these limitations could offer a more detailed understanding of the interactions between SWR, soil properties, and biological communities. Lastly, future studies should address the potential of SWR as an indicator of soil health, given the strong relationship between prokaryotic communities and SWR, and that SWR is a potential stress response that increases the resilience of natural habitats.

Author Contributions

Anne-Cathrine Storgaard Danielsen: conceptualization, investigation, formal analysis, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Cecilie Hermansen:** conceptualization, investigation, supervision, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Peter Lystbæk Weber:** investigation, supervision, writing – review and editing. **Deividas Mikstas:** investigation, writing – review and editing. **Charles Pesch:** investigation, writing – review and editing. **Lucas de Carvalho Gomes:** investigation, writing – review and editing. **Sebastian Gutierrez:** investigation, writing – review and editing. **Per Halkjær Nielsen:** funding acquisition, project administration, resources, supervision, writing – review and editing. **Mogens Humlekrog Greve:** supervision, project administration, writing – review and editing. **Per Møldrup:** conceptualization, supervision, writing – review and editing. **Signe Normand:** funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, writing – review and editing. **Lis Wollesen de Jonge:** conceptualization, supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, resources, writing – review and editing.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.